

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article discusses the demands placed on pedagogues in today's developing society, how to improve the professional competence of a pedagogue, how a pedagogue should be in the educational system today, and what his psychological competence should be.

Key words: Professional competence, competence, theory, intellectual, pedagogy, ability, methodology, coordination.

Modern society requires the education system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the task of "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a pool of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" was defined. Competent pedagogue - who is he? Questions arise, such as how the process of its formation takes place. In this context, it is important to define the meaning of the concepts "competence" and "competence". Not every teacher knows what "competence" means and how it differs from "competence". The concept of "competence" includes education, skills, abilities and experience of a pedagogue. In other words, it is his ability to perform a certain type of work. Actually, both terms are similar.

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, has a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes."

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastering of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to apply it in one's work. Professional competence is evident in the following situations

Summarizing the definitions and descriptions given to the concept of "professional competence of a teacher", it can be interpreted as follows: Professional competence of a teacher is one of the important aspects of professional competence in the activity of a pedagogue. liq represents all needs, abilities, skills, knowledge and interests.

Professionalism means not only certain knowledge, but also the attitude to work, specific features of work. The developed competences are immediately noticeable, because the professional pedagogue tries to develop his skills, strives to achieve certain goals and results, produces working values, and these usually correspond to the standard of the work process. Competence has a somewhat complicated meaning, because it requires not only the presence of knowledge, but also the ability to apply it. Competence can only be determined during extensive evaluation and observation.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that the pedagogue must have the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of professional activity and be able to apply them in practice, the pedagogue's ability to perform a certain work activity, this certain to have the necessary knowledge, skills, and experience in the field of work, to be a mature specialist in one's work, all these are the essence and content of the concept of competence. The work of pedagogues with pedagogical professional competence is effective and productive. Each pedagogue has his own professional competence. Through this, he participates in the pedagogical process. In order to become an active participant in this process, one should reflect the above qualities.

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